

Farmer saving part of the seed produced in community seed bank (Seed Granary)

In time of bumper harvest of quality seed, farmers have liberty to save part of the harvest at the community seed granary, can give out some to friends and relatives, exchange it with seed of another crop of preference or **sell the surplus as seed** to interested buyers for income.

Farmers are **NOT** advised to eat or use quality seed produced as grains.

Through easy access to quality seed, better crop production practices, establishment of community seed banks, empowering farmers with skills and knowledge, the CGS Project will guarantee sustainable food security, fight poverty and ameliorate effects of climate change.

Out of income generated from sale of quality seeds, the farmer has built a descent house with solar system, acquired animals and is able to educate his children

CGS project does not only focus on production and improving access to quality seeds, but the ultimate goal is to contribute towards the SDGs.

A farmer who has accessed knowledge, skills and better seed is able to get better yields for improved food security and increased incomes. As a result, he / she is able to meet the basic needs of the family and, thus have a better livelihood.

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STRENGTHENING SEED DELIVERY SYSTEM FOR DRYLAND CEREALS AND LEGUMES IN DROUGHT—PRONE AREAS OF UGANDA (W2A-PR-115 UG)

Also code named the “Cluster Granary Seed (CGS) Project” is of 3 years project to be implemented in Amuria, Kitgum and Kumi districts in Uganda.

The project seeks to address:

- Low productivity of dry-land cereals and legumes due to poor access to quality adaptable seed.
- High yield losses due to drought, floods, weeds, pests and diseases, and decreasing soil fertility.
- Limited farmer knowledge and skills on better farming practices for improved crop productivity.
- Limited capacity of farmers to produce and conserve quality seeds.

These challenges create insecure food and nutrition households that are economically constrained.

The project focuses on sustainable use and on-farm conservation of crop cultivars that adapt well in drought-prone areas for food security and adaptation to climate change.

This project is Funded by the European Union

FARMER TRAINING

An expert training farmers on quality seed production

- Farmers are mobilized into groups of 10 households.
- Demonstration gardens are set up strategically for training farmers and as technology dissemination points.
- Farmers are trained on quality seed production and group leadership.
- Various crop varieties are available to farmers for adaptation.
- Participatory variety selection is conducted for farmers to choose desired crop varieties.
- Farmers produce quality seed for conservation in granaries and surplus sold for income.

ACCESSING AND SAVING QUALITY SEED FROM THE SEED GRANARY

One farmer bringing in seed for saving, and another borrowing seed for planting

- After harvest farmers save part of the seed produced in seed granary.
- During planting and in times of seed shortage, farmers borrow seed from granaries.
- Amount of seed borrowed/saved is determined by the seed M & E committee.
- Seed granaries are constructed one per two farmer groups within the community and one large size granary at sub-county.
- Farmers manage the seed banks through leadership, book keeping, quality assurance and post-harvest handling.
- Diverse seed will be conserved as sources of breeding genetic materials at NaSARRI and NPGRC.

THE CLUSTER GRANARY SEED DELIVERY MODEL

EXPECTED OUTCOME

- Capacity of 600 farmers to produce quality seed built.
- Increased access to and availability of quality seed.
- Improved access to diverse crop varieties adapted to climate change
- Established at least 18 village seed granaries as seed reserves for sustainable use.
- Plant genetic materials centrally conserved at NaSARRI and NPGRC.
- Increased food security and better livelihoods of at least 300 households
- Strong links and collaboration with other stakeholders for sustainability.